

GENESIS, JESUS AND JOB

When God judged Adam and Eve, He gave them a hope — that the offspring of the woman would crush the serpent's head (Genesis 3:15). This offspring of the woman is the narrative center of the entire Bible; without this, it is impossible to explain why certain events are recorded in the Scriptures.

Adam thought his wife was the mother of all living (Genesis 3:20), because the offspring of the woman would come from this woman, defeat the serpent, and lead them back to life.

Eve thought her son Cain was that offspring (Genesis 4:1), but Cain, unable to accept that he was not pleasing to God, killed his brother and was banished by God (Genesis 4:12).

Cain thought his son Enoch was the offspring of the woman, so he named the city he built after his son (Genesis 4:17). A city is for defense against enemies. Cain did not trust God's protection (Genesis 4:15) and continued to rely on his own strength. Earlier he had sought to gain God's favor through murder.

The descendants of Cain continued to multiply with the hope of bringing forth the offspring of the woman, but their faith was cut off in the time of Lamech (Genesis 4:18-24). Lamech no longer sought salvation through the offspring of the woman, but through his own violence and intimidation (Genesis 4:23-24). The woman was no longer the mother of all living but became the audience for Lamech's boasting. Lamech inherited Cain's error and took pride in it.

Eve bore Seth. The descendants of Seth also multiplied with the hope of bringing forth the offspring of the woman. Seth's descendant Lamech thought

his son Noah was the offspring of the woman, who would deliver them from the curse (Genesis 5:29; Genesis 3:17-19).

In the time of Noah, humanity experienced the Great Flood. The Flood came because the earth was filled with violence (Genesis 6:11). The earth was filled with violence because the sons of God had relations with the daughters of men and they bore mighty men (Genesis 6:4). The “sons of God” refer to the descendants of Adam. Adam is the son of God (Luke 3:38). He was called the son of God because God gave him the Holy Spirit (Genesis 2:7), and the Spirit testifies that he is a son of God (Romans 8:14-17). In the Gospels, Jesus breathed on the disciples to give them the Holy Spirit (John 20:22). The “daughters of men” refer to the descendants of the “men” whom God created in Genesis 1 (Genesis 1:26-27). They had the image of God but did not have the Holy Spirit.

The sons of God married the daughters of men, and as a result they lost the Holy Spirit (Genesis 6:3). The problem was not the act of intercourse itself (Deuteronomy 21:10-13), but that the sons of God saw that the daughters of men were good (Genesis 6:2). If a believer fails to see the problems of an unbeliever and instead considers them good, it simply means he has lost his faith. Those who lost their faith became the Nephilim (Genesis 6:4). In ancient Hebrew, “Nephilim” means “the fallen ones.” These fallen ones lost the Holy Spirit because they abandoned faith in the offspring of the woman (Hebrews 10:29). They no longer trusted in the offspring of the woman to save their lives, but turned to violence and intimidation, and their descendants became mighty men. They walked in the way of Cain.

When everyone sought to save himself by violence and intimidation, the earth was filled with violence.

God chose Noah and saved his family from the Great Flood, so that the plan of the offspring of the woman could continue.

Noah's son Ham saw his father naked and told his brothers Shem and Japheth (Genesis 9:22). He committed the same error as Adam and Eve (Genesis 3:7), an error capable of destroying faith in the offspring of the woman. When Ham discovered that his father was merely a sinner, he no longer believed that his father's offspring could save them—just as Sarah, when she realized she had stopped menstruating, thought she could not bear the descendant of Abraham (Genesis 18:12). He told his brothers, but his brothers covered their father with a garment (Genesis 9:23). They imitated God's covering of Adam and Eve (Genesis 3:21) and preserved the faith. They believed that nothing is too hard for the Lord (Genesis 18:14; Luke 1:35). Therefore, the descendants of Ham were cursed to be servants (Genesis 9:24-27), because he did not believe in the offspring of the woman, and those who believe will reign as kings (Revelation 22:5).

The descendants of Noah continued to multiply, drawing nearer to the day when the offspring of the woman would be born.

When it came to Nimrod, a descendant of Ham, the descendants of Ham had a clear misunderstanding of the faith. They regarded God's grace and mercy (Genesis 9:3-5) as proof of their own achievements and thought that God therefore favored them more (Genesis 10:9). Like his ancestor Ham, Nimrod was skilled at exploiting the weaknesses of others to build up a sense of superiority. They did not realize that no human flesh is righteous before God (Exodus 20:26; Romans 3:20).

At Babel, the first place ruled by Nimrod, the famous Tower of Babel incident took place, and it arose from this same error. Those people wanted to prove

that they were closer to God by building a magnificent structure (Genesis 11:4). If they had succeeded, they would have been like the Pharisees, who believed that no prophet could arise from Galilee (John 7:52).

God chose Abram, a descendant of Shem, so that the offspring of the woman would come from him (Genesis 12:1-3). When Pharaoh tried to take his wife Sarai, which would have caused the plan of the offspring of the woman to fail, God prevented it (Genesis 12:10-20), just as He allowed Joseph to be sold into Egypt (Genesis 50:20), just as He sent Moses to lead Israel out of Egypt (Exodus 3:10), just as He raised up judges to save Israel (Judges 2:16), and just as He sent a messenger to tell Joseph and Mary to flee (Matthew 2:13). Lot, Abram's nephew—his two daughters also wanted to bring forth the offspring of the woman, but they used the wrong method, resulting in the ancestors of the Moabites and Ammonites (Genesis 19:31-38).

After Abram, God chose his son Isaac, then Isaac's son Jacob, and then Jacob's son Judah (Genesis 49:10). Judah's son Onan refused to fulfill his duty to produce offspring with his brother's widow Tamar, so God put him to death because he was unwilling to share in the offspring of the woman. Tamar used a stratagem and had relations with her father-in-law Judah, producing descendants. She was regarded as righteous because she wanted to bring forth the offspring of the woman (Genesis 38:26). From Judah's descendants, God chose David (2 Samuel 7:12-16); from David's descendants, God chose Joseph. The offspring of the woman, Jesus, was born of Joseph's wife Mary (Matthew 1:18-24).

Jesus fulfilled the Old Testament prophecies about Himself through His actions, confirming that He is the offspring of the woman. He also established the church to be His body and His wife (1 Corinthians 12:27; Ephesians 5:31-32). After His resurrection, Jesus was taken up into heaven and sat down

at the right hand of God. The church continues to grow according to His commands (Ephesians 4:7-16), awaiting His second coming to fulfill all prophecies (Revelation 21:1-8), just as the chosen people in the Old Testament were refined by God (Deuteronomy 8:3; Judges 3:1-4; Daniel 3:23-25) as they waited for the coming of the offspring of the woman.

Job was also one of the chosen people. He suffered not because of sin (Job 1:8; 42:7), but because his faith had drifted away from the offspring of the woman. His friends attacked him with the limitations of humanity (Job 4:17; 15:14-16), which was unreasonable, for God understands human weakness (Deuteronomy 23:20; Psalm 103:14; Matthew 19:8). Job believed that a righteous person could live a happy life, a faith that had no place for the offspring of the woman (Job 1:5; 3:1-26; 6:1-7:21). He knew about the offspring of the woman, but only after he had suffered intensely and endured repeated misunderstandings from his friends did he begin to turn to this offspring of the woman (Job 19:25-27). At first, Job was like the good man in the Gospels—he was good, but he did not follow Jesus because he was very powerful and felt no need (Matthew 19:16-22). As the debate progressed, Job finally began to think about the problem of the wicked (Job 21:7) and realized that he had no answer (Job 28:12).

God answered Job out of the whirlwind and resolved his confusion (Job 38:1). God did not remain aloof from suffering, but entered into the whirlwind Himself, foreshadowing the incarnation of Jesus, who came into the world to suffer (Hebrews 2:14-15; Matthew 8:24). God revealed His plan to Job (Job 38:2). This plan began with the foundation of the earth (Job 38:4), and that foundation is Jesus (Psalm 82:5-6; John 10:34-36; Colossians 1:16). This plan will cause all the chosen to rejoice (Job 38:7; Revelation 19:7), destroy the forces of the devil and the wicked (Job 38:11; 40:11-12; 41:1-34), and bring salvation to all creation (Job 38:36-39:30; Romans 8:19-22). Job was

comforted by this plan, for he had seen God with his own eyes (Job 42:5), just as Simeon was comforted when he saw Jesus with his own eyes (Luke 2:25-32). Jesus is the image of the invisible God (Colossians 1:15). Job knew that his suffering was not meaningless but was part of this great plan, just as Paul said: “For it has been granted to you on behalf of Christ not only to believe in him, but also to suffer for him” (Philippians 1:29).

And so Job became an example for later generations (James 5:11).